

Synthesis of novel bis-1,3,4-thiadiazoles, bis-1,2,4-triazoles and their antimicrobial activity

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Abstract : Condensation of sebacic acid dihydrazide (1) with aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates (2a-g) gives bis-(*N*-aryl/alkyl-thiocarbamido)-sebacic acid diamides (3a-g), which on reaction with *o*-phosphoric acid yields 1,8-bis-(2-aryl/alkylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-octanes (4a-g). 1,8-Bis-(3-mercapto-4-aryl/alkyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-octanes (5a-g) were obtained by a similar condensation of compounds (3a-g) with aqueous KOH, which on reaction with ethyl iodide in the form of dihydroiodides have been isolated (6a-g). These on basification with aq. ammonia solution afforded free bases (7a-g). Compounds (4a-g) on benzylation with benzoyl chloride and NaOH affords benzoyl derivatives (8a-g). The structures of all these compounds were confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral data and evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against gram positive and gram negative bacteria.

Keywords : Synthesis, bis-1,3,4-thiadiazole, bis-1,2,4-triazole, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Thiadiazoles^{1,2}, triazoles^{3,4} and their derivatives are known for their biological activities⁵⁻⁷. As a part of our research programme to explore the new route for the synthesis of various heterocyclic compounds, we now report the synthesis of various 1,8-bis-(2-aryl/alkylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-octanes (4a-g) and 1,8-bis-(3-mercapto-4-aryl/alkyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-octanes (5a-g) in the present communication.

Results and discussion

The parent compound sebacic acid dihydrazide (1) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of sebacic acid (0.01 mol) and thionyl chloride (0.02 mol) for 20 min, followed by the addition of hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol). It was transformed into bis-(*N*-aryl/alkyl thiocarbamido)-sebacic acid diamides (3a-g) by condensing with different aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates (2a-g) in chloroform medium. Compounds (3a-g) were found to be desulphurizable when boiled with alkaline lead acetate solution.

1,8-Bis-(2-aryl/alkylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-octanes (4a-g) were obtained by the intramolecular cyclocondensation of bis-(*N*-aryl/alkyl thiocarbamido)-sebacic acid diamides (3a-g)⁸ with *o*-phosphoric acid. While further condensation of bis-(*N*-aryl/alkyl thiocarbamido)-sebacic acid diamides (3a-g) with aqueous

KOH afforded 1,8-bis-(3-mercapto-4-aryl/alkyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-octanes (5a-g), which on reaction with ethyl iodide in 1 : 2 ratio yielded dihydroiodide of 1,8-bis-(3-ethyl mercapto-4-aryl/alkyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-octanes (6a-g). These compounds (6a-g) on basification with dilute ammonium hydroxide solution afforded free bases (7a-g). Compounds (4a-g) on benzylation with benzoyl chloride and NaOH in 1 : 2 ratio yielded bis-benzoyl derivatives (8a-g) (Scheme 1).

The structure assignments of all these compounds were based on elemental analysis and spectral data (vide Experimental).

Antimicrobial activity :

The title compounds (4a-g) and (5a-g) were screened for their antimicrobial activity using cup-plate diffusion method^{9,10}. The bacterial organisms used included both gram positive and gram negative strains like *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *P. vulgaris* and *Shigella flexneri*. Sensitivity plates were seeded with a bacterial inoculum of 1×10^6 CIU/ml and each well diameter (10 mm) was loaded with 0.1 ml of test compound solution (1000 μ g/ml) in DMF. So that concentration of each test compound was 100 μ g/ml. The zones of inhibition were recorded after incubation for 24 h using vernier calliper. Inhibition zones record of the compounds clearly indicated that 4a, 4c and 5d, 5f were highly active against *E. coli*, *B. subtilis* and

Where,

- 2-8 : a : R = p-tolyl
 b : R = m-tolyl
 c : R = o-tolyl
 d : R = phenyl
 e : R = m-chlorophenyl
 f : R = p-chlorophenyl
 g : R = t-Butyl

Scheme 1

S. aureus and moderately active against *Shigella flexneri*. Majority of the compounds were found inactive against *P. vulgaris* and *E. coli*.

Screening of the title compounds for antifungal acti-

vity using paper disc method^{11,12} showed that **4c**, **4e** and **5c** and **5f** were highly active against *A. niger*, whereas other compounds showed low to moderate activity. The zones of inhibition were recorded after incubation for 48 h at 37 °C.

Experimental

The melting points of all synthesized compounds were recorded using hot paraffin bath and are uncorrected. Chemicals used were of A.R. grade. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded with TMS as internal standard using CDCl_3 and $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ as solvents. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrometer in the range $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in nujol mull and as KBr pellets. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX-102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer. Purity of the compounds was checked on silica gel-G plates by TLC.

Parent compound sebacic acid dihydrazide (**1**) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of sebacic acid (0.01 mol) and thionyl chloride (0.02 mol) for 20 min, followed by the addition of hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol).

Synthesis of bis-(*N-p*-tolyl thiocarbamido)-sebacic acid diamide (**3a**) :

A mixture of sebacic acid dihydrazide (**1**) (0.01 mol) and *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate (**2a**) (0.02 mol) in chloroform (10 ml) was refluxed for 2.0 h. Then chloroform was distilled off and granular solid mass was obtained. It was crystallized from ethanol and identified as bis-(*N-p*-tolyl thiocarbamido)-sebacic acid diamide **3a**, (85%), m.p. $202\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Found : C, 59.01; H, 6.75; N, 15.85; S, 12.04. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$: C, 59.09; H, 6.81; N, 15.90; S, 12.12%); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{13,14}$: 3407 (NH) , 1678 (C=O) , 1350 (C-N) , 1225 (N-N) , 1062 (C=S) , 812 cm^{-1} (*p*-substituted benzene); ^1H NMR ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO}-d_6$) : 9.71 (2H, s, NH, NH), 9.58 (2H, s, NH, NH), 9.34 (2H, s, NH, NH), 6.84–7.92 (8H, m, Ar-H), 2.32 (6H, s, Ar- CH_3), 2.17 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-(A)}$), 1.50 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-(B)}$), 1.21 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-(C)}$).

Similarly, other diamides **3b-g** were obtained using different aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates.

Synthesis of 1,8-bis-(2-*p*-tolylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-octane (**4a**) :

To 2.0 g of bis-(*N-p*-tolyl thiocarbamido)-sebacic acid diamide (**3a**) was placed in *o*-phosphoric acid (10.0 ml) with constant stirring for 30 min at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured in water. A cream coloured precipitate thus obtained, was filtered off, dried and recrystallized from aqueous ethanol (70%) to yield white coloured solid. It was found to be non-desulphurizable on boiling with alkaline plumbite solution indicating absence of $>\text{C}=\text{S}$ group and identified as 1,8-bis-(2-*p*-tolylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-octane **4a**, (80%), m.p. $210\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Found : C, 63.29; H, 6.44; N, 17.08; S, 13.02. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2$: C, 63.41; H,

6.50; N, 17.07; S, 13.00%); ν_{max} : 3435 (NH) , 1600 (C=N) , 1350 (C-N) , 1180 (N-N) , $815\text{ (p-substituted benzene)}$, $669\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ (C-S)}$; ^1H NMR ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO}-d_6$) : 9.58 (1H, s, NH), 9.65 (1H, s, NH), 6.82–7.68 (8H, m, Ar-H), 2.36 (6H, s, Ar- CH_3), 2.26 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-(A)}$), 1.65 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-(B)}$), 1.29 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-(C)}$); MS : m/z (relative intensity) 492 (M^+ , 30), 493 ($\text{M}+1$, 33), 477 (20), 401 (22), 302 (34), 260 (10), 232 (15), 150 (30), 91 (35).

Similarly other compounds (**4b-g**) were obtained from (**3b-g**) : **4b** (77%), m.p. $199\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Found : C, 63.33; H, 6.45; N, 17.01; S, 12.96. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2$: C, 63.41; H, 6.50; N, 17.07; S, 13.00%); **4c** (78%), m.p. $215\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Found : C, 63.35; H, 6.32; N, 17.05; S, 13.01. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2$: C, 63.41; H, 6.50; N, 17.07; S, 13.00%); **4d** (79%), m.p. $205\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Found : C, 61.94; H, 5.97; N, 18.04; S, 13.65. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2$: C, 62.06; H, 6.03; N, 18.10; S, 13.19%); **4e** (77%), m.p. $210\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Found : C, 54.01; H, 4.75; N, 15.68; S, 12.01. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$: C, 54.03; H, 4.87; N, 15.75; S, 12.00%); **4f** (82%), m.p. $218\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Found : C, 53.96; H, 4.85; N, 15.70; S, 11.98. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$: C, 54.03; H, 4.87; N, 15.75; S, 12.00%); **4g** (75%), m.p. $222\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Found : C, 56.52; H, 8.34; N, 19.75; S, 14.89. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2$: C, 56.60; H, 8.49; N, 19.81; S, 15.09%).

Synthesis of 1,8-bis-(3-mercapto-4-aryl/alkyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-octane (**5a**) :

To 2.0 g of bis-(*N-p*-tolyl thiocarbamido)-sebacic acid diamide (**3a**) was placed in (5%, 10 ml) aq. KOH with constant stirring for 30 min and allowed to stand for 2 to 3 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured in water. A yellow coloured precipitate thus obtained, was filtered, dried and recrystallized from aqueous ethanol (70%) to yield whitish yellow solid. It was found to be non-desulphurizable on boiling with alkaline plumbite solution indicating absence of $>\text{C}=\text{S}$ group and identified as 1,8-bis-(3-mercapto-4-*p*-tolyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-octane **5a**, (82%), m.p. $202\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Found : C, 63.25; H, 6.28; N, 16.98; S, 12.95. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2$: C, 63.41; H, 6.50; N, 17.07; S, 13.00%); ν_{max} : 3041 (SH) , 1602 (C=N) , 1350 (C-N) , 1222 (N-N) , $810\text{ (p-substituted benzene)}$, $722\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ (C-S)}$; ^1H NMR ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO}-d_6$) : 9.54 (2H, s, SH, SH), 7.03–7.85 (8H, m, Ar-H), 2.35 (6H, s, Ar- CH_3), 2.14 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-(A)}$), 1.49 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-(B)}$), 1.21 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-(C)}$); MS : m/z (relative intensity) 492 (M^+ , 13.5), 493 ($\text{M}+1$, 40), 477 (18), 401 (11.5), 302 (36), 232 (75), 115 (30), 107 (48), 91 (39.5).

Similarly other compounds (**5b-g**) were obtained from (**3b-g**) : **5b** (79%), m.p. 225 °C (Found : C, 63.25; H, 6.22; N, 17.10; S, 13.01. Calcd. for $C_{26}H_{32}N_6S_2$: C, 63.41; H, 6.50; N, 17.07; S, 13.00%); **5c** (77%), m.p. 215 °C (Found : C, 63.35; H, 6.27; N, 17.08; S, 12.98. Calcd. for $C_{26}H_{32}N_6S_2$: C, 63.41; H, 6.50; N, 17.07; S, 13.00%); **5d** (78%), m.p. 218 °C (Found : C, 61.92; H, 5.94; N, 17.92; S, 13.55. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{28}N_6S_2$: C, 62.06; H, 6.03; N, 18.10; S, 13.79%); **5e** (80%), m.p. 210 °C (Found : C, 53.98; H, 4.58; N, 15.65; S, 11.87. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{26}N_6S_2Cl_2$: C, 54.03; H, 4.87; N, 15.75; S, 12.00%); **5f** (84%), m.p. 215 °C (Found : C, 54.07; H, 4.74; N, 15.60; S, 11.90. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{26}N_6S_2Cl_2$: C, 54.03; H, 4.87; N, 15.75; S, 12.00%); **5g** (76%), m.p. 228 °C (Found : C, 56.48; H, 8.30; N, 19.70; S, 14.93. Calcd. for $C_{26}H_{36}N_6S_2$: C, 56.60; H, 8.49; N, 19.81; S, 15.09%).

Synthesis of 1,8-bis-(3-ethyl mercapto-4-p-tolyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-octane (7a) :

1,8-Bis-(3-mercapto-4-p-tolyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-octane (**5a**) (0.01 mol) and ethyl iodide (0.02 mol) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 1.5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured on a little crushed ice. When a off white solid precipitated was crystallized from aqueous ethanol (70%) and identified as dihydroiodide of 1,8-bis-(3-ethyl mercapto-4-p-tolyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-octane **6a**, (81%), m.p. 175 °C.

Similarly, other compounds (**6b-g**) were prepared from (**5a-g**) : **6b** (79%), m.p. 182 °C; **6c** (78%), m.p. 185 °C; **6d** (77%), m.p. 179 °C; **6e** (82%), m.p. 180 °C; **6f** (85%), m.p. 178 °C; **6g** (75%), m.p. 183 °C.

On basification of **6a** with dilute ammonium hydroxide solution, a free base **7a** was obtained, it was crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 169 °C (Found : C, 65.59; H, 7.04; N, 15.18; S, 11.57. Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{40}N_6S_2$: C, 65.69; H, 7.29; N, 15.32; S, 11.67%); ν_{max} : 1601 (C=N), 1351 (C-N), 1222 (N-N), 661 cm^{-1} (C-S); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$ + DMSO- d_6) : 6.95-7.68 (8H, m, Ar-H), 2.33 (6H, s, Ar- CH_3), 2.49 (4H, q, $-CH_2$), 2.07 (4H, t, $-CH_2$ (A)), 1.49 (4H, m, $-CH_2$ (B)), 1.25 (4H, m, $-CH_2$ (C)), 1.07 (6H, t, $-CH_3$). This reaction was extended to synthesized free bases, **7b-g** : **7b**, m.p. 177 °C (Found : C, 65.54; H, 7.30; N, 15.04; S, 11.38. Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{40}N_6S_2$: C, 65.69; H, 7.29; N, 15.32; S, 11.67%); **7c**, m.p. 165 °C (Found : C, 65.44; H, 7.10; N, 15.28; S, 11.70. Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{40}N_6S_2$: C, 65.69; H, 7.29; N, 15.32; S, 11.67%); **7d**, m.p. 170 °C (Found : C, 66.45;

H, 6.87; N, 16.09; S, 12.28. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{36}N_6S_2$: C, 64.61; H, 6.92; N, 16.15; S, 12.30%); **7e**, m.p. 175 °C (Found : C, 56.88; H, 5.69; N, 14.15; S, 10.65. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{34}N_6S_2Cl_2$: C, 57.04; H, 5.77; N, 14.26; S, 10.86%); **7f**, m.p. 168 °C (Found : C, 56.94; H, 5.71; N, 14.20; S, 10.68. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{34}N_6S_2Cl_2$: C, 57.04; H, 5.77; N, 14.26; S, 10.86%); **7g**, m.p. 168 °C (Found : C, 59.87; H, 8.97; N, 17.23; S, 13.25. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{44}N_6S_2$: C, 60.00; H, 9.16; N, 17.50; S, 13.33%).

Synthesis of 1,8-bis-[2-(p-tolyl, benzol)amino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl]-octane (8a) :

To a suspension of 1,8-bis-(2-p-tolylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-octane (**4a**) (0.01 mol) in sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 10 ml) was added with vigorous shaking benzoyl chloride (0.02 mol) within half an hour. The reaction mixture was cooled below 5 °C and poured into little crushed ice, when a cream coloured solid was precipitated. It was crystallized from aqueous ethanol (70%) to yield 1,8-bis-[2-(p-tolyl, benzol)-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl]-octane **8a**, (81%), m.p. 185 °C (Found : C, 68.40; H, 5.65; N, 11.87; S, 9.08. Calcd. for $C_{40}H_{40}N_6S_2O_2$: C, 68.57; H, 5.71; N, 12.00; S, 9.14%); ν_{max} : 1690 (C=O), 1602 (C=N), 1351 (C-N), 1222 (N-N), 818 (p-substituted benzene), 667 cm^{-1} (C-S); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$ + DMSO- d_6) : 6.81-7.98 (18H, m, Ar-H), 2.39 (6H, s, Ar- CH_3), 2.29 (4H, t, $-CH_2$ (A)), 1.66 (4H, m, $-CH_2$ (B)), 1.29 (4H, m, $-CH_2$ (C)).

This reaction was extended to synthesized other bis-benzoyl derivatives (**8b-g**) : **8b** (77%), m.p. 182 °C; **8c** (79%), m.p. 195 °C; **8d** (80%), m.p. 178 °C; **8e** (78%), m.p. 187 °C; **8f** (81%), m.p. 184 °C; **8g** (74%), m.p. 230 °C.

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